

Evaluating the Role of Local Government in Disaster Management in Vadodara

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ABSTRACT

Vadodara in Gujarat, India is subjected to a number of disaster management challenges due to geographical location and environmental hazards like floods, among others. This paper reviews disaster preparedness, responses, and recovery mechanisms that have been put in place in the city, emphasizing the role of local government in mitigating such risks. This paper outlines infrastructural vulnerabilities, gaps in governance accountability, and limited community engagements impeding efficient disaster management. Drawing on best practices from the domestic case study of Surat and the international case study of Bangkok, this paper carries policy recommendations that can be utilized to enhance Vadodara's disaster resilience.

Keywords: *Disaster management, Local Governance, Vadodara, Environmental Risks*

1. INTRODUCTION

Vadodara, is a city located in the western Indian state of Gujarat. Geographically, the city is positioned at 22°18'N latitude and 73°11'E longitude, situated on the fertile plains between the Mahi and Narmada rivers. Vadodara is located at an elevation of approximately 39 meters (128 feet) above sea level and lies along the banks of the Vishwamitri River, which plays a crucial role in its water management system. The Mahi River to the north and the Narmada River to the south flank the region, contributing to the city's agricultural productivity, while also presenting certain geographical risks. (Chandam, 2017)

1.1 Geographical and Environmental Risks

Due to its proximity to the river, its natural topography, tropical climate, and rapid development, there are a variety of geographical or environmental risks that Vadodara faces. These include flooding, scarcity of water, earthquakes, air pollution, and environmental degradation.

1.1.1 Flooding

Vadodara experiences frequent fluvial flooding, especially during the monsoon season (June to September), when heavy rainfall leads to the overflow of the Vishwamitri River. Historically, the Vishwamitri has been prone to flooding, particularly in low-lying areas like Sayajigunj, Karelibaug, and Fatehgunj (Tnn, 2024). Urbanization has exacerbated this problem as impervious surfaces (roads, pavements, and buildings) prevent water from being absorbed into the ground, leading to increased runoff. Further complicating matters, rural urban migration has led to construction on floodplains and wetlands, reducing the city's natural flood mitigation capacity. (Singh & International Centre for Environment Audit and Sustainable Development, 2022)

1.1.2 Water Scarcity

Despite getting an average annual rainfall of 950 mm, the city of Vadodara faces acute shortages of water throughout the dry months starting from October up to May. With the Vishwamitri River—the primary source of surface water getting dried up during the summer months, the dependence shifts on groundwater resources entirely (Samachar, 2024). Excessive dependence on groundwater has led to aquifer depletion, with reports of declining water tables in large parts of the city. In addition, industrial effluent and agricultural runoff continue to adulterate the groundwater; high concentration levels of pollutants such as fluoride, arsenic, and nitrates have been recorded. This contamination affects not only the quantity of water available for drinking purposes but also poses long-term public health risks. (Vyas, 2023)

1.1.3 Environmental Degradation

Rapid urbanization has led to the degradation of Vadodara's natural environment. As the city expands, its green cover and natural wetlands that are vital in controlling flood and filtering water continue to be destroyed. Encroachment of restricted areas surrounding the Vishwamitri River has led to reduced groundwater recharge capacity and increased stormwater runoff, intensifying both water scarcity and flood risks. The loss of natural vegetation on the bank is increasing the rate of soil erosion. (Deshpande & Desai, 2016)

1.2 Role of Local Governance

The governance structure for disaster management in Vadodara is based on the Gujarat State Disaster Management Act of 2003, which established the Gujarat State Disaster Management Authority (GSDMA). The GSDMA coordinates disaster risk reduction activities at the state level and works closely with district authorities, including the Vadodara Municipal Corporation (VMC) (Gujarat State Disaster Management Authority, n.d.). VMC is also entrusted with the responsibility to implement disaster preparedness, response, and recovery activities at the local level. The roles and responsibilities regarding preparation for and response to and recovery from disasters of different levels are listed in the City Disaster Management Plan.

1.2.1 Flood Forecasting and Warning Systems

The VMC, in collaboration with the Vadodara Irrigation Circle, maintains a flood forecasting system for the Vishwamitri Basin. Data recorded regarding the water level and rainfall are sent in real time to the City Engineer who issues flood warnings. There are wireless stations installed upstream of the city that receive important information about the river gauges and rainfall that allow for timely issuance of flood alerts and the authorities can plan evacuation accordingly.

1.2.2 Pre-Monsoon Preparedness

The maintenance of the stormwater drains, identification of flood shelters, survey of the most vulnerable infrastructure among other activities like pruning dangerous trees, clearing blockades in the drainage system, and demolition of dilapidated structures that are prone to collapsing are activities carried out before monsoon begins. Public awareness campaigns are conducted to educate citizens on disaster preparedness, particularly in flood-prone areas.

1.2.3 Disaster Preparedness

The Vadodara Municipal Corporation (VMC) coordinates with the Fire and Emergency Services, the Police Department, and Public Health services, to ensure that resources such as food, medicine, and clean drinking water are available and ready to be deployed during a disaster. The city has established a Command and Control Centre that monitors real-time data from the Vishwamitri River during floods. This center coordinates the deployment of emergency

personnel to affected areas, ensuring that timely responses are executed when needed. In the event of a flood, temporary shelters are set up in schools, community halls, and other public buildings to accommodate displaced families. These shelters are set up with basic amenities to support those in need. Furthermore, evacuation plans are regularly updated and communicated to residents in flood-prone areas.

1.2.4 Disaster Response

The City Disaster Management Committee headed by the Municipal Commissioner mobilizes support from all other departments. The VMC coordinates with fire services, police, and local volunteers to evacuate people from flood-affected areas. Rescue teams are equipped with boats and other necessary equipment to navigate floodwaters and people. The city's health department, led by the Chief Medical Officer, is responsible for making medical services available for the treatment of flood victims and preventing the outbreak of waterborne diseases. Temporary medical camps are set up in evacuation shelters to provide first aid and basic healthcare.

The recovery phase focuses on restoring normalcy in flood-affected areas, ensuring that infrastructure is repaired and that displaced residents can return to their homes as quickly as possible. The VMC conducts a thorough damage assessment to identify the extent of destruction caused by the disaster. This includes evaluating the condition of homes, roads, bridges, and public utilities. Based on the assessment, the municipal authorities prioritize the rebuilding of essential infrastructure.

Post-disaster reconstruction efforts aim to build back better, with a focus on improving the resilience of infrastructure to future disasters. For example, buildings in flood-prone areas are required to be constructed above the known flood level, and drainage systems are upgraded to handle increased runoff. Rehabilitation efforts include providing psychological support to flood victims, as well as assistance in restoring livelihoods, particularly for those who depend on agriculture or informal sector jobs.

2. METHODOLOGY

This paper underlines a qualitative collection, analysis, and synthesis of information on disaster management issues in the city of Vadodara. This includes a comprehensive literature review of available government reports, current disaster management plans of concerned cities, and best

practices that have been implemented by other cities with almost similar geographical and environmental hazards.

In order to detect challenges in Vadodara keeping all aspects in mind, information has been sought through direct primary data sources, such as the Gujarat State Disaster Management Plan, and from indirect secondary data sources, including academic papers, news articles from papers like The Times of India, The Indian Express, Economic Times, Gujarat Samachar as well as, Vadodara Municipal Corporation reports, UNDP reports, UNDRR reports, Gujarat Institute of Disaster Management website, National Disaster Management Authority website, and so on.

The exclusion criteria used was excluding studies published before 2010 to retain the focus on current practice and challenges. Opinion pieces, editorials, or review articles devoid of any empirical data supporting the arguments were also excluded. Non-English articles were not considered due to language barriers. Articles that were paywalled or were less accessible were also disregarded. Research focusing on disaster management strategies outside of Gujarat or India was excluded unless it provided insights applicable to Vadodara. This paper collates data from key themes related to disaster preparedness, response mechanisms, and recovery strategies with a special focus on the function of local government in these processes.

3. Case Study: Surat – Successful Disaster Management Amid Similar Geographical and Environmental Risks

For a city in India that has successfully implemented disaster management practices while facing similar geographical and environmental risks as Vadodara, Surat in Gujarat stands out as a strong example. Surat has historically faced challenges related to flooding, rapid urbanization, and industrial pollution but has managed to transform its disaster management approach after the devastating floods of 2006.

3.1 Background and Geographical Context

Surat is a major city in Gujarat, located on the banks of the Tapi River at coordinates 21°10'N and 72°50'E. Similar to Vadodara, Surat is situated in a fertile floodplain and has an elevation of about 13 meters (43 feet) above sea level. The city is close to the Arabian Sea, making it vulnerable to both floods and cyclones (Surat Municipal Corporation, n.d.). Surat is also near the Ukai Dam upstream, further increasing its risk of flooding during periods of heavy rainfall or

dam releases (Mehta, 2024). Like Vadodara, Surat also faces water scarcity issues in dry seasons despite its relatively high annual rainfall of around 1,200 mm (Think Hazard, n.d.). The city is part of Seismic Zone III, meaning it faces moderate earthquake risks. Rapid urbanization and industrialization have exacerbated the city's environmental challenges, including deforestation, depletion of groundwater, and shrinking wetlands. (Bansal, 2018)

3.2 Historical Flooding and its Impact

Surat has been historically vulnerable to flooding, primarily caused by the overflow of the Tapi River during the monsoon season. The city experienced significant floods in 1994, 1998, and 2006. In 2006 Surat faced its worst flood with water rising as high as 12 meters and flooding 75 percent of the city, therefore affecting 2.2 million people (Parikh et al., 2017). The flood in 2006 was, therefore, a turning point in the disaster management strategies of Surat after which the city government felt the need for a more systematic and proactive approach in disaster preparedness and mitigation.

3.3 Disaster Management Strategies Adopted in Surat

The city of Surat initiated serious reforms in their flood management strategy after the devastating floods of 2006. The primary focus was given to flood forecasting and early warning systems. A Flood Early Warning System (FEWS) was installed in the city which integrates real time monitoring of rainfall, river stages, and dam releases. (Resilience Strata, 2011)

The system, operated by the Surat Municipal Corporation in coordination with the Indian Meteorological Department and the Central Water Commission, has helped the authorities provide timely flood warnings. These are conveyed to the public via SMS, the local news, and public address systems, ensuring that residents are well-informed and can take necessary precautions. (Agarwal, 2024)

Apart from FEWS, SMC has been in direct contact with the Ukai Dam authorities regarding the release schedule of the dam water. It is now tuned into real-time flood forecast models, according to which the dam water is released gradually, instead of releasing large volumes of water during the peak rainfall period to avoid the sudden surge in the Tapi River. Such proactive approaches cut down the risk of flooding substantially in urban areas. SMC has upgraded the city's drainage, especially those places that experience waterlogging. The SMC has undertaken desilting and

maintenance of natural drains and rivers to ensure that they aren't blocked during monsoon season. (Agarwal, 2024)

Besides that, it carries out extensive pre-monsoon preparedness activities each year. This involves cleaning up stormwater drains, canals, and creeks so that the water can flow easily whenever there are heavy rains and prevent clogging (Agarwal, 2024.). Moreover, for flood resilience, embankments along critical points of the Tapi River have been reinforced and raised, particularly in residential and commercial areas near the riverbanks. SMC has mapped flood-prone areas using Geographic Information Systems to develop contingency plans for the evacuation of residents well in advance. (Surat City Resilience Strategy, n.d.)

Community participation is a pivotal part of Surat's disaster management success story. It has been running various campaigns for creating awareness amongst its citizens regarding flood risks, evacuation routes, and helpline numbers. The community meetings, school, and social media are harnessed to create awareness on disaster preparedness. Additionally, mock drills for flood evacuation and emergency response are conducted annually in collaboration with local communities, businesses, and schools to ensure effective responses during real flood events. Volunteer networks are created in every neighborhood in order to help in the case of evacuation, provide first aid, and disseminate real-time information from SMC during floods. (Government of India et al., 2006)

To mitigate environmental degradation, Surat has taken steps towards climate resilience with the help of urban reforestation to bring back the green cover and wetland ecosystem, which works as natural defense against floods. These wetlands behave like sponges at the time of flood and absorb the rainwater and flash flood water. (Green Flagship, 2023)

Technological integration has also helped in strengthening the disaster management abilities of Surat. SMC uses Geographical Information Systems to monitor real-time flood conditions so that the authorities can gauge vulnerable zones and deploy resources more efficiently in the case of a disaster. Furthermore, a 24x7 Emergency Operations Centre has been established for real-time surveillance and monitoring of critical infrastructure such as bridges, roads, and water bodies during a flood. (National Disaster Management Authority, n.d.)

4. Case Study: Bangkok, Thailand – Best International Disaster Management Amid Similar Geographical and Environmental Risks

4.1 Geographical and Environmental Context

Bangkok is located in the Chao Phraya River delta, only a few meters above sea level, which makes it highly vulnerable to riverine flooding, much like Vadodara's vulnerability to the Vishwamitri River floods. The city experiences significant flooding during the monsoon season, as well as occasional flash floods caused by tropical storms (Dpa, 2021). Rapid urbanization has also reduced the natural drainage capacity, exacerbating flood risks. Additionally, Bangkok faces challenges related to groundwater depletion, pollution, and environmental degradation, similar to Vadodara's issues with water scarcity and industrial pollution. (Bremard, 2022)

4.2 Disaster Management Strategies

Bangkok has invested significantly in structures meant to tackle the frequent flooding it is used to facing. The local government has built a long stretch of dams, levees, and floodgates along the Chao Phraya River, which together regulate the flow of the river across the rainy, monsoon seasons to restrict spillage into the city. These floodgates enable authorities to discharge water from reservoirs well in advance of heavy rains, thereby preventing downstream flooding.

Additionally, there is a wide network of underground tunnels and canals, similar to Tokyo's G-can project but on a smaller scale, to which the rainwater is diverted during heavy rains. (World Highways, 2013) They have also created artificial retention ponds to hold excess rainwater temporarily when it floods or is about to flood. This is very similar to the 'Water Squares' flooding solution of Rotterdam but tailored to Bangkok, at a more economical level. (Gerretsen, 2022) Bangkok has also invested in green infrastructure by expanding urban parks and creating green roofs to absorb the rain to reduce runoff. (Garfield, 2018)

The city employs real-time flood monitoring systems that integrate data from weather stations, river gauges, and satellites to enhance disaster preparedness. The Thai Meteorological Department and the BMA coordinate to issue timely flood warnings among the residents of the city via telephonic communication or community alert systems. Government awareness campaigns in disaster preparedness involve practice drills and education at schools as well as at the neighborhood level so that citizens know how to respond in case of flooding (Governor & Berkowitz, n.d.).

Flood zoning regulations are also enforced in Bangkok to prohibit any new construction in high flood risk areas. As an alternative, any new construction in those areas has to be done using flood mitigation tactics such as elevating the foundation of the building, installing stormwater management systems, and having flood barriers (Katharangsiporn, 2012). The BMA has also taken up the task to upgrade roads, improve bridges and drainage systems and reduce overall infrastructure vulnerability.

Integrated Water Resource Management policies have been implemented in Bangkok to balance the use of surface water, groundwater, and rainwater. Under these policies, local authorities collaborate with the community to foster water conservation habits, by rainwater harvesting and prevention of water wastage in domestic and industrial uses. This is done to avoid conditions of water scarcity simultaneously reducing dependency on over-extracted groundwater, which contributes to land subsidence that exacerbates flood risks. (Anukularmphai et al., n.d.)

5. Current Challenges in Local Governance in Disaster Management in Vadodara

5.1 Infrastructure Vulnerability

Infrastructure in Vadodara is becoming increasingly overburdened with rapid urbanization and inadequate long-term planning. These vulnerabilities severely cripple the city's capacity to respond to, and recover from, disasters like floods. Vadodara's drainage systems are very old and have proven inadequate for the volumes of stormwater that the city experiences. As a result, constant waterlogging and floods occur, especially in low lying areas. In particular, stormwater drains are often clogged due to poor maintenance, siltation, and waste dumping, which reduces their capacity (Tnn, 2024a). A lot of the burden is hence placed on natural channels like the Vishwamitri River. However the natural floodplains have been encroached upon by illegal constructions and informal settlements. This encroachment has made it difficult for the river to flow freely, exacerbating flooding issues. (The Indian Express, 2024)

Lack of retention ponds, buffer zones, and unmanaged natural floodplains have aggravated the situation of flooding. The floods normally destroy roads, which are an integral part of evacuation and response. Potholes, poorly maintained bridges, and a lack of proper stormwater drainage along roadways make the transportation network vulnerable, often leading to traffic congestion and delayed emergency responses (Dave, 2024). A majority of the facilities and buildings have

been developed without considering the local topography and issues of flooding; therefore, many newly developed areas get submerged even in cases of moderate rains.

Also, approximately one-third of the population of Vadodara resides in unorganized slums, situated in the floodplains, that lack basic amenities such as drainage, pure water, and decent shelter. Consequently, residents of these settlements are disproportionately affected during floods. The city's governance system has struggled to effectively manage these areas, which are often neglected in disaster preparedness and recovery planning. (Lobo & Centre for Culture and Development, 2015)

Moreover, many critical facilities such as hospitals, emergency shelters, and government buildings are not designed to withstand flooding or other disaster risks. Accessibility to those places becomes a huge issue during disasters because the roads leading to those places get submerged (National Disaster Management Authority, n.d.). Similarly, the floods disrupt drinking water service and electricity. Vadodara still has to develop appropriate systems that would ensure continuity of such services during disasters-increasing risks of long disruption of services following flooding (Times of India, 2024). The recent past has highlighted these vulnerabilities, for example when 8 to 12 feet of water from torrential rains in August 2024 submerged the city of Vadodara for almost three successive days, with indiscriminate development and encroachment around the Vishwamitri River having obstructed the normal flow course of the river. (Raja and Sharma, 2024)

5.2 Accountability of Governance Agencies

One of the problems of disaster management in Vadodara is the lack of definition of accountability between various governance agencies that are actually responsible for preparedness, response, and recovery. Multiple agencies are involved in managing different aspects of disaster response, often leading to delays and inefficiencies. The roles and responsibilities of these agencies are not clearly defined; hence, bureaucratic delays along with gaps in coordination occur during emergencies as agencies end up trying to shift the responsibility on one another. (Second Administrative Reforms Commission, 2006)

During any disaster, different departments like public works, health, water, and electricity have to work in liaison with each other. This results in slow decision-making due to poor

communication and the absence of an integrated mechanism of information sharing. For example, flood forecasting data given by the Meteorological Department or the Irrigation Department is not always acted upon promptly by the municipal authorities. The slow bureaucratic processes in government agencies result in delayed decisions, especially during critical times when timely action is needed to mitigate disaster risks. In the case of flooding, this could mean delayed evacuations, slow deployment of emergency services, and prolonged recovery efforts. (Tere, 2024)

5.3 Corruption and Lack of Transparency

Long-standing problems with corruption in local governance have resulted in the misallocation of funds meant for Vadodara's infrastructure development, emergency preparedness, and post-disaster recovery. Corrupt practices have caused delays and cost overruns in stormwater drainage and flood-proofing projects, significantly impairing the city's ability to manage disasters. (Counterview, 2024) For example, it is alleged that VMC has been awarding tenders to the contractors who quote higher bids of 32-37% more than the estimates, resulting in significant financial losses for the city. The various resources used in disaster management, including rescue operation equipment, medicine supplies, and fund allocations towards the relief aren't tracked properly or accounted for which leads to shortages during actual crises. (Samachar, 2024a)

In absence of an effective monitoring mechanism, it is tough to ensure that resources are utilized properly and reach those in need during disasters. The city has implemented building codes that require the building in high-risk zones to be flood-resistant; (Gujarat Urban Development Department, 2017). However, these building codes are often neglected and enforcement has been slack. Most of the new constructions, especially informal settlements, do not follow disaster-resilient designs, making them vulnerable to any disaster might occur.

Furthermore, there is a lack of effective monitoring systems to ensure that pre-disaster mitigation efforts—such as cleaning drainage systems and maintaining flood gates—are carried out regularly. Regular inspections of critical infrastructure, flood forecasting systems, and public safety measures are often overlooked, leading to inadequate disaster preparedness. (Samachar, 2024a)

Vadodara's residents will be left vulnerable in the case of a calamity if corruption is not reduced and increased transparency is not introduced in the distribution and administration of resources.

5.4 Community Engagement

The participation of the community is one of the most crucial aspects for proper disaster management. Vadodara has been irregular and ineffective in that sense.

Vadodara's disaster resilience has been undermined by inadequate community involvement. The city has made inconsistent and ineffective attempts to involve the public in disaster management, despite the fact that community involvement is essential. The city's overall capacity to withstand disasters has been weakened by this lack of substantive citizen involvement. Widespread involvement of citizens is lacking, and its reduction in capacity for disaster resilience is minimal. Vadodara's efficacious disaster governance suffers from neglect of citizens. Meaningful citizens are central to disaster governance but Vadodara has sporadic and feeble attempts on bringing public into disaster management. Overall strengthening of its resilience capacity for any disaster will be hindered by its reduced substantive citizen-duty. (UNDP, n.d.)

Gujarat State Disaster Management Authority and Vadodara Municipal Corporation have prepared the plans for disaster management, however those plans do not offer much scope for community involvement in their preparedness activities. (Gujarat State Disaster Management Authority, n.d.) . Most residents, especially in informal settlements, have little idea of what flood risk they face, let alone the actions to be taken when a disaster strikes. The population is still mostly ignorant of flood evacuation routes, emergency shelter locations, and first aid protocols related to disasters, even in the face of insufficient public awareness campaigns. This often results in the exclusion of traditional knowledge and needs relevant to vulnerable groups, hence hindering an efficient response to disasters effectively from the grassroots. Effective grassroots response to disasters is hampered by this lack of involvement, which frequently results in the marginalization of traditional knowledge and ignores the unique requirements of vulnerable communities.

The city has few training programs aimed at arming its citizens with information that would enable them to tackle floods and other disasters. Mock drills have been conducted, but even so, these are largely confined to schools and government offices. Rarely are mock drills conducted for the greater community. In most effective systems of disaster management, local committees

form the structure for grassroots responses to calamities. Unfortunately, this kind of a setup is a far cry in Vadodara, particularly in slum areas where the inhabitants are most vulnerable. Involving the community leadership in planning and implementation of disaster management will contribute much to the local response structure and overall preparedness. (VMC, 2022)

6. Recommendations

6.1 Technological Upgradation

Technological advancement is necessary to make the drainage system of Vadodara resilient to seasonal flooding. Upgrading its storm water drainage system essentially involves increasing the capacity of all the existing drains and installing a flood monitoring system such as ENVIRA, which uses real-time data from weather stations, river gauge, and satellites. Water level, temperature, and humidity sensors installed at an autonomous monitoring station and provides data on the above-mentioned parameters to a central dashboard. (Envira, 2023)

When the water level exceeds the preset level, a flood warning SMS or email is sent to local authorities to take immediate action (Fondriest Environmental, Inc., 2015). The integration of the system with existing drainage infrastructure in Vadodara will easily enhance flood management potential. It would require the installation of a monitoring station on the Vishwamitri River, apart from low-lying areas of Sama and Karelibaug, to understand the flow and risks of flooding. This enables coupling ground-based data with satellite tools for a more efficient regional analysis. This includes investment in better drainage infrastructure and monitoring systems, by which the city would be better placed to handle floods and reduce damage to properties and communities of vulnerability whenever heavy rainfall prevails. (Fondriest Environmental, Inc., 2015)

6.2 Infrastructure

To effectively manage seasonal flooding in Vadodara, it is crucial to incorporate innovative solutions such as artificial retention ponds and installing strategic floodgates along the Vishwamitri River. These gates will regulate water flow, preventing overflow into residential areas during heavy rains, thereby reducing property damage and enhancing public safety. Floodgates are large gates or barriers installed in key areas like dams or riverbanks. When the water level is normal, the gates are usually open, allowing water to flow naturally. But if heavy

rain or a flood is expected, the gates can be closed or partially closed to hold back or control the water when levels pass a predefined limit, stopping it from spilling over into surrounding areas. Once the water level drops or the risk passes, the gates can be opened again to let the water flow normally. This helps manage flood risks and protect nearby communities. By utilizing automated systems linked to real-time monitoring data from weather stations and river gauges, Vadodara can ensure timely closure of the gates in response to rising water levels (Britannica, 1999). This approach not only mitigates immediate flood risks but also supports long-term urban resilience by protecting critical infrastructure and fostering community confidence in local disaster management efforts. This is already successful in Surat where floodgates have proven successful in safeguarding urban populations against severe flooding events. (Ahluwalia et al., 2015)

Retention ponds are designed to capture excess rainfall and maintain a permanent pool of water, which allows for sedimentation and natural filtration processes. These ponds function by collecting stormwater runoff from impervious surfaces such as roads and rooftops, directing it into the pond where sediments settle to the bottom. Aquatic plants surrounding the pond help absorb pollutants, improving water quality through biological uptake (Natural Water Retention Measures, n.d.). In cities like Bangkok, artificial retention ponds have been successfully integrated into urban planning to manage stormwater effectively, showcasing their ability to reduce flood risks while providing recreational spaces for communities (Admin & Admin, 2024). For Vadodara, potential locations for these artificial retention ponds include low-lying neighborhoods such as Sama, Akota, Karelibaug, and Harni, all of which have experienced significant flooding during heavy rains. Additionally, parks like Sayaji Garden and Sardar Patel Planetarium can be transformed into retention areas to capture runoff while enhancing community green spaces (The Indian Express, 2024). By strategically placing these retention ponds in these locations, Vadodara can improve its flood resilience while promoting environmental sustainability and community well-being.

6.3 Awareness

Most importantly, there is a dire need to increase significant awareness among the poor and flood-affected populations living in informal settlements within Vadodara regarding how to build resilience and preparedness during these disaster times. These communities often face significant challenges during disasters, including the loss of all their belongings due to flooding, which can

lead to delayed evacuations as residents may hesitate to leave their homes and possessions behind. Therefore, awareness initiatives must be broad-based and long-term amongst such populations and not sporadic or confined to the bureaucracy. There are many such successful examples in awareness skits designed for less literate populations in India, mainly on elementary healthcare, civic duties, and legal rights. The "Mitti Ka Khel" skit in rural Maharashtra informs villagers about soil conservation and efficient use of water through relatable characters and scenarios. Similarly, the "Dharamveer" skit in Uttarakhand sensitized the people about flood threats and how to react in case of a disaster by showcasing a local hero who demonstrates evacuation routes. These initiatives demonstrate that localized content significantly improves community engagement and response rates. Localized interventions in Vadodara need to be concentrated in areas like Sama, Karelibaug, and Harni, especially in informal settlements prone to flooding. (Kumar, 2023b)

The dissemination of information using local languages increases the potential reach to all community members, who then understand messages on disaster preparedness. In effect, evacuation drills and skits will enhance readiness and ensure that the residents understand the proceedings about evacuation. By fostering a culture of continuous preparedness through targeted awareness campaigns, the local government can help the low-income community take the lead by in times of disasters, ultimately reducing their vulnerability and enhancing the community's resilience.

6.4 Maintenance

Regular maintenance of the drainage system is an essential requirement for effective control of floods in Vadodara, especially before monsoon seasons. This means proper cleaning of the drain to clear debris, sediment, or blockages that may limit water flow. Additionally, servicing drainage infrastructure—such as inspecting and repairing any damaged components—ensures that the systems can withstand the pressures of increased water flow during storms. This proactive approach is one of the best practices followed by Surat. The SMC undertakes a comprehensive maintenance program for its drainage systems every year prior to monsoon (Gogoi & Gogoi, 2024). Among these, some of the most important practices are:

- a. Annual Desilting: The SMC outsources private agencies to desilt manholes and drainage lines in the city. This makes sure that debris and sediment are removed from where they

are accumulated so water flows freely across the lines during heavy rains. (Surat Municipal Corporation, n.d.)

- b. Integrated Command and Control Centre: ICCC is provided in Surat with almost 3,300 CCTV cameras all over the city. The CCTV monitors are in real-time keeping track of drainage performance so that such blockages or other problems are detected by authorities immediately. It also feeds instant data on water levels and flow rates enabling proper interventions. (Surat Municipal Administrative Control (SMAC) Centre, n.d.)
- c. Inspections and Repairs. SMC regularly inspects the drainage infrastructure in order to determine if there is any damages present and has them repaired. Systematic inspection and repair of drainage components maintain the integrity of drainage systems. (Surat Municipal Corporation, n.d.)
- d. Community Engagement Surat: It empowers the community and motivates them to engage in cleanliness initiatives and to report issues pertaining to the drainage systems. The locals can participate in cleaning drives and inform about choking issues or defects in the drainage systems.

Such practices adopted in Vadodara will enable local authorities to strengthen drainage systems.

6.5 Regulations

Increasing construction regulations in Vadodara is the need of the hour to reduce flood risks especially in high-risk areas (Kumar, 2023). This includes not allowing new constructions in flood-prone zones and disbanding illegally formed informal settlements in restricted areas. It may also take some of the effective regulations taken up by the Surat Municipal Corporation for initiatives taken in Vadodara. The city, for instance, should enforce highly stringent zoning regulations which should not allow a single new development in identified flood prone, low lying areas along the Vishwamitri River and drainage channels as not to allow further construction where water is most likely to be accumulated. Additionally, Vadodara can conduct thorough assessments to identify informal settlements that pose significant risks to safety and infrastructure. The city should provide alternative shelter to the settlement residents through resettlement in safer places with some service provisions. More importantly, there will be a strong monitoring mechanism: satellite images, drones surveying construction activities from

time to time, and detecting illicit constructions. Such technology and safety standards would mean that the zoning could go into effect immediately.

6.6 Innovative Urban Planning

Innovative urban planning, using Bangkok as an inspiration, would greatly enhance flood resilience in Vadodara. Green roofs would come in handy in absorbing rainwater, while runoff would be at a minimal rate, hence decreasing the load in the drainage system. It is a multilevel system that involves the top layer of vegetation that acts as the catch for the rainwater, followed by the growing medium that retains water, and then the drainage layer that helps excess water be taken away and kept at bay from the building. Such systems allow green roofs to hold up to 75% of the falling rainwater during heavy events, gradually releasing it through evaporation and transpiration, which cools the surrounding, and mitigating the urban heat island effect. (Green Roof Company, n.d.)

In addition to green roofs, Vadodara can implement permeable pavements as an innovative urban planning strategy for flood management. Permeable pavements consist of materials that allow water to infiltrate through the surface, reducing surface runoff and promoting groundwater recharge. This mechanism helps manage stormwater effectively by allowing rainwater to percolate through the pavement and into the soil below, thereby decreasing the risk of flooding during heavy rains. (Express News Service, 2023)

It is important to make rainwater harvesting mandatory in Vadodara and provide rainwater harvesting systems to new constructions as well as to the existing homes. This, in turn, will hugely reduce the dependency on the municipal water supply and also regulate the stormwater. Rainwater falling from rooftops can be collected and stored for irrigation or other non-potable usages, reducing stress on the city's drainage when there is heavy rainfall. In fact, already there have been successful models of the same at Sama, Harni, and Ajwa, especially where community initiatives have made them more aware and opened their homes to these systems. (Grewal et al., 2020).

6.7 Geographic Information Systems (GIS)

Application of geographic information systems is effective in the context of flood management for defining areas prone to flooding and monitoring those in real-time. The same case applies to Vadodara, which may create advanced flood hazard maps where it could identify vulnerable areas based on topography, historical flooding data, and other hydrological models using GIS technology. Through this, authorities can better predict which areas are most vulnerable and to really target resource deployment during a disaster more effectively. With the integration of various data sets such as land use, soil types, and elevation, GIS can provide an integrated view concerning the risk involving floods to plan and allocate emergency responses effectively. (Hagos et al., 2022)

6.8 Emergency Shelters

The establishment of specific emergency shelters that are earmarked for flood-related disasters is a pressing requirement in Vadodara to save the inhabitants, especially residents in low-lying areas. Shelters should be placed in safe zones, and all essential items such as food, water, medical aid, and communication facilities should be arranged for them. During flooding events, the Vadodara Municipal Corporation (VMC) can activate these shelters to provide immediate refuge for displaced individuals and families. By ensuring that these shelters are designed to accommodate large numbers of people, the city can offer a safe environment until conditions improve. Inspiration can be drawn from the emergency setup system in Surat. The VMC should conduct awareness programs with the people regarding locations of such shelters followed by mock evacuation drills. Community feedback should also be incorporated during the planning of such shelter facilities to ensure that they serve the needs of the most vulnerable individuals appropriately.

7. Conclusion

The policy paper discussed the critical need for innovative strategies to enhance flood resilience in Vadodara, focusing on the implementation of green roofs, permeable pavements, and mandatory rainwater harvesting systems. It emphasized the importance of utilizing Geographic Information Systems (GIS) to map flood-prone areas and monitor real-time conditions, enabling more efficient resource allocation during emergencies. Additionally, the establishment of

designated emergency shelters for residents in low-lying areas was highlighted as a vital component of disaster preparedness.

By adopting these comprehensive measures, including maintenance, regulations, GIS, emergency shelters, technological upgrades, innovative urban planning, awareness initiatives, and infrastructure improvements, Vadodara can significantly improve its capacity to manage flooding, protect vulnerable communities, and promote sustainable urban development. Drawing inspiration from successful case studies like Bangkok, which has implemented extensive flood control infrastructure and green spaces to manage its flooding challenges, and Surat, which transformed its disaster management approach post-2006 floods through early warning systems and community involvement, Vadodara can adopt best practices tailored to its unique context. The recommendations outlined in this paper aim to foster a proactive approach to flood management that not only addresses immediate risks but also contributes to the long-term resilience and well-being of the city's residents.

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